

THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT QUALITY, BRAND IMAGE, AND BRAND AMBASSADOR ON MS GLOW PURCHASE DECISIONS IN BATURITI, TABANAN REGENCY, BALI PROVINCE

Ni Ketut Oni Widarianti¹, Ni Made Ary Widiastini², Putu Indah Rahmawati³

Management Science Study Program, Faculty of Postgraduate Studies, Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha, Indonesia
E-mail: niketutoniwidarianti@gmail.com¹, ary.widiastini@undiksha.ac.id², indah.rahma@undiksha.ac.id³

Received	: 20 March 2026	Accepted	: 17 April 2026
Revised	: 30 March 2026	Published	: 03 May 2026

Abstract

This study aims to describe and examine the influence of several variables, namely: (1) product quality, (2) brand image, (3) brand ambassador, and (4) product quality, brand image, and brand ambassador simultaneously on the purchasing decisions of MS Glow products in Baturiti, Tabanan Regency, Bali Province. The population of this study consists of all MS Glow consumers in the Baturiti area. The sample was determined using purposive sampling, with the criteria that respondents must have made at least two purchases, resulting in a total of 180 respondents. This study is designed as causal quantitative research. Data were collected using a questionnaire instrument containing statements related to product quality, brand image, brand ambassador, and purchase decisions. The data were analyzed using simple linear regression and multiple linear regression to determine the partial and simultaneous effects between variables. The results show that: (1) product quality has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions; (2) brand image has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions; (3) brand ambassador has a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions; and (4) product quality, brand image, and brand ambassador simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions of MS Glow products in Baturiti. Therefore, improving product quality, strengthening brand image, and selecting the right brand ambassador can serve as effective strategies to enhance the purchasing decisions of MS Glow consumers in Baturiti.

Keywords: *Brand Ambassador, Brand Image, Purchase Decision, Product Quality.*

INTRODUCTION

Skincare refers to a range of products and practices used to maintain, protect, and enhance the health and appearance of the skin. According to Kotler and Keller (2016), skincare products are classified as consumer goods that are purchased routinely to satisfy both functional and psychological needs. Meanwhile, Baumann (2009) explains that skincare functions to maintain skin balance, protect against external factors such as pollution and UV rays, and address specific skin issues according to individual needs. With the growing public awareness of skin health and appearance, the skincare industry has experienced rapid development. Consumers now consider not only the functional benefits of products but also product quality, brand image, and the public figures representing the brand when making purchase decisions. One skincare trend predicted to remain popular in 2023 is Skin Minimalism (Gallinaro, 2023). Skin Minimalism is a skincare concept that emphasizes simplifying product usage steps while focusing on essential skin needs. This concept encourages consumers to choose skincare products that are high-quality, effective, and safe without using an excessive number of steps (Doe, 2023).

In contrast to the 10-Step Korean Skincare trend, which involves using multiple product types in a single routine, the Skin Minimalism trend is simpler and more practical. Typically, the routine includes only essential basic skincare, such as a gentle facial wash with balanced pH, a moisturizer to maintain skin hydration, and sunscreen for UV protection (Doe, 2023). This trend indirectly increases consumer attention to product quality, as the products used must deliver optimal results despite being limited in number. The Skin Minimalism trend, emphasizing effectiveness and simplicity, encourages consumers to be more selective when choosing skincare brands. Consumers prioritize practical, easy-to-use products that provide optimal results according to their skin needs. This situation has intensified competition among skincare brands, requiring each brand to maintain consumer trust and interest amid changing skincare trends. According to the Top Brand Award, several skincare brands have ranked as top brands based on the Top Brand Index from 2022 to 2025. Erha Clinic consistently

occupied the first position with the highest percentage compared to other brands. Natasha Skin Care ranked second, followed by brands such as ZAP Clinic, MS Glow, and London Beauty Center, competing in the top-tier skincare brand category. This indicates that competition among skincare brands in Indonesia is intense, with relative variation in brand index percentages from year to year. The Top Brand Index data show that some brands, including Erha Clinic and Natasha Skin Care, consistently remain in the top five, while MS Glow is also recognized as a brand capable of entering the Top Brand Index. Data from the 2022–2025 Top Brand Index indicate significant changes in MS Glow's position within the beauty product industry. In 2022, MS Glow held a 3.20% share, reflecting low consumer awareness and preference compared to other beauty brands, suggesting that MS Glow was still in the early stages of brand building. Positive developments occurred in 2023, with MS Glow's Top Brand Index increasing to 13.20%, reflecting the effectiveness of marketing strategies, expanded product distribution, and rising consumer interest. However, this increase does not yet fully reflect sustainable consumer purchase decisions.

Changes in Top Brand Index percentages for each brand reflect the dynamic nature of consumer preferences for skincare products. The Top Brand Index measures brand performance through three main aspects: mind share, market share, and commitment share. Mind share reflects a brand's ability to occupy a position in the consumer's mind within a product category. Market share represents the brand's strength in the market, related to consumer purchase behavior. Commitment share indicates the brand's ability to encourage repeat purchases in the future. Thus, the Top Brand Index serves as an important indicator for assessing the strength and competitiveness of a skincare brand. MS Glow's presence in the Top Brand Index demonstrates that the brand is fairly well recognized by the public. In the Baturiti region, MS Glow is also used by consumers to meet daily skincare needs. This condition warrants further study given changing skincare trends and increasing competition among brands. Consumers face numerous choices in the market, making the decision-making process more selective and complex. Therefore, studying consumer purchase decisions for skincare products, particularly MS Glow in Baturiti, is important to understand consumer behavior in selecting products that match their needs and preferences.

Purchase decision is the process experienced by consumers when buying a product. Kotler and Keller, (2012) state that purchase decisions include the stages of need recognition, information search, alternative evaluation, purchase decision, and post-purchase behavior. Viatama and Rizal, (2023) describe purchase decision as an individual's response to various stimuli, both internal and environmental. Skincare products add further complexity due to the many brands with differing characteristics. Intense competition in the skincare industry requires consumers to consider multiple factors before purchasing a product (Andika & Putra, 2025). Initial observations through questionnaires distributed to MS Glow consumers in Baturiti revealed variations in purchase commitment, buying habits, willingness to recommend, and repurchase intention. Some consumers were not fully confident choosing MS Glow over other brands. Consumer loyalty had not yet been strongly established, as some still tried other brands or followed temporary trends. The willingness to recommend the product and intention to repurchase were uneven, highlighting the need to enhance consumer satisfaction and confidence.

Product quality is a primary factor influencing purchase decisions. Armstrong & Kotler, (2012) define product quality as a product's ability to perform its function effectively, including durability, reliability, accuracy, ease of use, and other attributes that provide added value to users. Tjiptono (2016) adds that product quality reflects key characteristics such as performance, reliability, ease of use, and aesthetics. Armstrong & Kotler, (2012) emphasize that product quality encompasses functional and emotional aspects, so high-quality products meet needs while providing greater satisfaction. High-quality products build trust, increase loyalty, and positively influence purchase decisions. Tjiptono, (2016) identifies six indicators of product quality: performance, durability, conformance, features, reliability, and aesthetics. Performance refers to the product's ability to meet consumer expectations based on measurable attributes. Durability reflects how long the product functions optimally before its quality declines, affecting economic value. Conformance measures the extent to which a product meets standards and expectations, while features emphasize additional attributes that enhance value and appeal. Reliability refers to the likelihood that a product functions without failure, and aesthetics include appearance, scent, and texture, which influence a positive emotional experience (Anggarawati & Putra, 2024).

Initial observations from MS Glow consumers in Baturiti revealed that product performance was rated well, as results matched claims such as brightening and moisturizing the skin. Reliability was also perceived as high because the product was safe for use without causing irritation. Other indicators received lower perceptions. Product durability raised concerns as effects did not last long. Product variety was still limited, and consumers expected more options suitable for different skin types and needs. Ease of use was less practical for products requiring multi-step application. Perceptions of aesthetics, including scent and texture, varied, as some consumers

expected more appealing formulas or packaging. These findings confirm that product quality is a crucial consideration in purchase decisions, especially when comparing MS Glow to other skincare brands. Previous studies support these findings. Sarifuddin *et al.*, (2025) indicate that product quality positively affects purchase decisions. Isnaini *et al.*, (2024) and Arsyah *et al.*, (2024) emphasize product quality as a significant factor in purchasing behavior. Studies by Kasinem, (2020) and Karina, (2023) show that service quality does not always significantly impact satisfaction, confirming that product quality remains the primary factor. Brand image refers to consumers' perceptions of a brand, reflected through the associations held in their minds. Kotler and Keller, (2012) state that brand image is a reflection of the various associations consumers possess. Ferrinadewi (2008) emphasizes that brand image is formed from consumers' memories related to brand associations. Kotler, (2007) describes brand image as consumers' perceptions and beliefs manifested through associations stored in memory. Firmansyah, (2018) adds that brand image encompasses what consumers think and feel when they see or hear a brand name, while Nugroho, (2003) highlights that a positive brand image develops when consumers have sufficient experience with an organization's actual performance. Armstrong & Kotler, (2012) define brand image as the combination of consumers' perceptions and feelings toward a brand name or symbol.

According to Kotler and Keller, (2012), brand image indicators include brand identity, brand personality, brand associations, and brand benefits or advantages. Brand identity reflects consumers' ability to recognize and differentiate MS Glow from other brands. Brand personality represents a distinct, modern, and trustworthy character. Brand associations describe perceived quality and inherent value, while brand benefits and advantages relate to the brand's ability to fulfill needs and provide superior value compared to competing brands. Initial observations of consumer perceptions regarding brand image reveal that brand identity and personality are rated positively, as consumers can easily recognize the products and perceive them as modern and reliable. Brand associations and benefits/advantages require further improvement, as some competing products offer additional features or benefits that MS Glow lacks. Previous studies support these findings: Sarifuddin *et al.*, (2025), Puspitasari *et al.*, (2024) and Putri & Ramadhan (2024) indicate that brand image significantly affects purchase decisions. Other research, such as Kasinem, (2020), shows that the influence of brand image on consumer satisfaction is not always significant, highlighting the need for consistent product quality to strengthen brand image.

Brand ambassadors are a widely used marketing strategy to enhance brand appeal and influence consumer purchase decisions. A brand ambassador is an individual with a level of popularity, reputation, and personal capability leveraged by a company to promote a brand or product to the public. According to Kertamukti, (2015), a brand ambassador is a public figure or celebrity who endorses a product based on their image, ability, and reputation. Lea-Greenwood, (2012) explains that brand ambassadors serve as marketing communication tools to build relationships between the brand and the public while boosting sales. Furthermore, Dinnie, (2015) emphasizes that the effectiveness of a brand ambassador lies in their ability to consistently communicate the brand's values, message, and image to consumers. Sagia and Situmorang (2018) note that brand ambassadors function not only as promotional media but also as icons representing the brand, fostering consumer trust and emotional attachment. In practice, the success of a brand ambassador can be measured by visibility, such as social media followers. MS Glow collaborates with prominent Indonesian public figures as brand ambassadors, including Nagita Slavina with 76.8 million Instagram followers, Ria Ricis with 37 million, Lesti Kejora with 28.9 million, and Happy Asmara with 6.8 million. These large followings indicate a wide communication reach and strong potential to disseminate information, shape brand perception, and influence consumer purchase decisions.

Brand ambassador indicators include visibility (popularity), credibility (expertise), attractiveness, and power (influence). Visibility reflects the brand ambassador's recognition and ability to enhance brand awareness. Credibility refers to the ability to deliver product information accurately and convincingly. Attractiveness includes appearance, communication style, and charisma, while power indicates the ability to influence consumer behavior, including purchase decisions (Ariasih, 2025). Initial observations regarding brand ambassadors indicate that MS Glow consumers consider them popular, easily recognizable, credible, and attractive, prompting interest in trying the products. Some consumers feel that brand ambassadors are less directly engaged with local consumers, limiting their influence. Appearance or communication style is perceived as less relevant by some, restricting attractiveness and influence to specific segments. Previous studies support these findings: Sarifuddin *et al.*, (2025), Isnaini *et al.*, (2024), Hata & Huda, (2024), Wibowo & Putra, (2024), and Habibulloh *et al.*, (2024) indicate that brand ambassadors significantly influence purchase decisions. However, their influence is limited if consumers prioritize product quality or price (Arta *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, MS Glow products contain active ingredients suitable for the skin conditions of Baturiti residents. Ingredients such as vitamin C, niacinamide, collagen, hyaluronic acid, and

THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT QUALITY, BRAND IMAGE, AND BRAND AMBASSADOR ON MS GLOW PURCHASE DECISIONS IN BATURITI, TABANAN REGENCY, BALI PROVINCE

Ni Ketut Oni Widarianti *et al*

natural plant extracts help moisturize, brighten, and maintain skin elasticity, making them relevant for consumers in highland areas with different temperature and humidity compared to coastal regions. Antioxidant content also helps protect the skin from sun exposure and local pollution, important for Baturiti residents who engage in outdoor activities. Brand ambassadors in Baturiti play a key role in shaping perceptions and enhancing purchase decisions, as the selected celebrities have wide influence and can provide trusted product recommendations to local consumers. Their involvement in promotional campaigns, both online and through local events, helps build loyalty and raises awareness of the products’ benefits that align with consumer skin needs.

The selection of Baturiti as the research location is justified. First, Baturiti has diverse demographic characteristics, including education level, occupation, and skincare consumption habits, facilitating the collection of valid and representative data. Second, local awareness of skincare is high, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of consumer perceptions regarding product quality, brand image, and brand ambassadors. Third, Baturiti’s cooler and more humid climate compared to coastal areas makes the evaluation of MS Glow skincare products relevant, as local consumers can assess the effectiveness of moisturizers, brightening agents, and antioxidants.

Based on the discussion above, there is a gap between theory and practice regarding product quality, brand image, and the role of brand ambassadors in purchase decisions. Some indicators that should support purchase decisions, such as product quality, brand image, and brand ambassadors, show varying perceptions among consumers. This indicates that companies need to pay closer attention to consumer preferences and experiences to enhance marketing effectiveness. With proper product quality management, a positive brand image, and strategic use of brand ambassadors, MS Glow can gain greater consumer value and drive higher purchase decisions. Based on these considerations, the author is motivated to study the topic: “The Influence of Product Quality, Brand Image, and Brand Ambassadors on MS Glow Purchase Decisions in Baturiti, Tabanan Regency, Bali Province.”

METHOD

The research design employs a causal quantitative approach to examine the influence of product quality, brand image, and brand ambassadors on the purchasing decisions of MS Glow products in Baturiti. The study was conducted from April to December 2024, with subjects consisting of consumers who had made at least two purchases, while the research objects include four variables: product quality (X1), brand image (X2), brand ambassador (X3), and purchasing decision (Y). The population comprises all MS Glow consumers in Baturiti, with samples selected using purposive sampling based on domicile, age ≥17 years, and purchase experience, resulting in 90–180 respondents. Primary data were collected through an online questionnaire based on 18 indicators using a Likert scale and analyzed using multiple linear regression with IBM SPSS version 25.

Table 1. Review of Previous Studies

Author	Article Title	Results and Discussion	Link
A.C. Ninef, N. L. W. S. Telagawathi (2025)	The Influence of Product Quality and Brand Image on Purchase Decisions of Filano Motorcycles in Buleleng District, Singaraja City	Product quality and brand image have a positive and significant influence on the purchase decision of Filano motorcycles in Buleleng District, Singaraja City.	https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/Prospek/article/view/104884/35846
Mahadewi, M. M. S., & Yulianthini, N. N. (2024)	The Influence of Brand Image and Product Quality on Purchase Decisions of MS Glow in Singaraja	Brand image and product quality have a positive and substantial influence on the purchase decisions of MS Glow products at Abadi Cosmetic Store, Singaraja.	https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/Prospek/article/view/69084/32088
Rahmadhini, N., & Telagawathi, N. L. W. S. (2023)	The Influence of Product Quality and Brand Image on Purchase Decisions of Asus Laptops in Singaraja City	Product quality has a positive and significant influence on purchase decisions, while brand image has a negative and significant influence on the purchase decisions of Asus laptops in Singaraja City.	https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/BISMA-JM/article/view/66093
Sagita, K. D. A. T., & Telagawathi, N. L. W. S.	The Influence of Product Quality and Brand Image on Purchase Decisions of Xiaomi Smartphones among	Product quality and brand image significantly influence the purchase decisions of Xiaomi smartphones among Management students of the 2020 cohort	https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/Prospek/article/view/82964/33216

THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT QUALITY, BRAND IMAGE, AND BRAND AMBASSADOR ON MS GLOW PURCHASE DECISIONS IN BATURITI, TABANAN REGENCY, BALI PROVINCE

Ni Ketut Oni Widarianti et al

(2025)	Management Students of Undiksha	at Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha.	
Suastini, L. S., & Yulianthini, N. N. (2025)	The Influence of Brand Image and Product Quality on Purchase Decisions of Skintific Skincare Products at Queen Beauty Cosmetic Store, Singaraja	Brand image and product quality have a positive and significant influence on purchase decisions of Skintific skincare products at Queen Beauty Cosmetic Store, Singaraja.	https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/Prospek/article/view/80671/33206
Telagawathi, N. L. W. S., & Susila, G. P. A. J. (2019)	The Influence of Brand Image and Product Quality on Purchase Decisions of Honda Beat Motorcycles	Brand image and product quality significantly influence purchase decisions.	https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/BISMA-JM/article/view/21975/13594
Widyasari, L., & Ariasih, M. P. (2024)	The Influence of Brand Image and Product Quality on Purchase Decisions of Skintific among Undiksha Management Students	Brand image and product quality have a positive and significant influence on purchase decisions of Skintific among Undiksha Management students.	https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/Prospek/article/view/79052/32102
M. Andika, K. E. S. Putra (2025)	The Influence of Consumer Perception and Brand Ambassador on Purchase Decisions of Converse Shoes among Undiksha Students	Consumer perception and brand ambassadors have a positive and significant influence on purchase decisions of Converse shoes among Undiksha students.	https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/Prospek/article/view/94223/35842
M. C. L. Dewi, K. E. S. Putra (2024)	The Influence of Brand Ambassador and Product Quality on Purchase Decisions of Cosmetic Products (Study on Oriflame Consumers in Buleleng District)	Brand ambassadors and product quality have a significant influence on purchase decisions.	https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/BISMA-JM/article/view/64433
N. L. K. R. Utami, N. L. W. S. Telagawathi (2025)	The Influence of Product Quality and Brand Image on Purchase Decisions of Wardah Skincare	Product quality and brand image have a significant influence on the purchase decisions of Wardah skincare products.	https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/Prospek/article/view/81231/33208
N. K. A. N. Dita, M. P. Ariasih (2025)	The Influence of Brand Ambassador and Electronic Word of Mouth on Purchase Decisions of Somethinc Facial Moisturizer in Singaraja City	Brand ambassador and electronic word of mouth have a significant influence on purchase decisions of Somethinc facial moisturizer in Singaraja City.	https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/BISMA-JM/article/download/99551/33821
K. A. Susriyawati, I. N. Suarmanaya sa (2025)	The Influence of Product Quality and Brand Image on Repurchase of Scarlett Whitening at Queen Beauty Singaraja	Product quality and brand image have a positive and significant influence on repurchase of Scarlett Whitening at Queen Beauty Singaraja.	https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/Prospek/article/view/97916/33944

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Classical Assumption Tests

Normality Test

According to Ghozali, (2011), the criteria are as follows:

- a. If the data points are distributed around the diagonal line and follow its direction, or the histogram shows normal distribution pattern, the regression model meets the normality assumption.

THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT QUALITY, BRAND IMAGE, AND BRAND AMBASSADOR ON MS GLOW PURCHASE DECISIONS IN BATURITI, TABANAN REGENCY, BALI PROVINCE

Ni Ketut Oni Widarianti *et al*

- b. If the data points deviate far from the diagonal line and/or do not follow its direction, or the histogram does not show a normal distribution pattern, the regression model does not meet the normality assumption.

Figure 1. Normal P-Plot Graph
(Source: SPSS 25.0 for Windows Output)

Based on the Normal P-Plot (Figure 1), the residual points are distributed around the diagonal line and follow a straight-line pattern, indicating that the data distribution does not deviate significantly and approximates a normal distribution.

Table 2. Results of the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		180
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.48877186
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.060
	Positive	.035
	Negative	-.060
Test Statistic		.060
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

(Source: SPSS 25.0 for Windows Output)

To further confirm data accuracy, the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test was conducted (Table 2). The test statistic value is 0.060 with a significance level of 0.200, which is greater than 0.05, indicating that the data are normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity is assessed using Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values:

- a. Tolerance > 0.10 and VIF < 10 indicate no multicollinearity.
- b. Tolerance > 0.10 and VIF > 10 indicate multicollinearity.

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Coefficients ^a		
	Collinearity Statistic		
	Tolerance	VIF	Keterangan
Product Quality (X ₁)	0,722	1,385	Bebas Multikolinieritas
Brand Image (X ₂)	0,766	1,306	Bebas Multikolinieritas
Brand Ambassador (X ₃)	0,676	1,480	Bebas Multikolinieritas

(Source: SPSS 25.0 for Windows Output)

THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT QUALITY, BRAND IMAGE, AND BRAND AMBASSADOR ON MS GLOW PURCHASE DECISIONS IN BATURITI, TABANAN REGENCY, BALI PROVINCE

Ni Ketut Oni Widarianti et al

Based on Table 3, VIF values for product quality (X1), brand image (X2), and brand ambassador (X3) are 1.385, 1.306, and 1.480, respectively, all below 10. Tolerance values are 0.722, 0.766, and 0.676, all above 0.10, confirming no multicollinearity in the regression model.

Heteroskedasticity Test

The heteroskedasticity test is conducted to assess whether there is inequality in the variance of residuals across all observations in a linear regression model. If heteroskedasticity occurs, the residual variance is not constant, which can lead to inaccuracies in model estimation. If the heteroskedasticity assumption is not met, the regression model is considered invalid as a predictive tool.

Figure 2. Scatterplot Graph
(Source: SPSS 25.0 for Windows Output)

Based on the scatterplot (Figure 2), the residual points are randomly distributed along the horizontal axis without forming any specific pattern, indicating the absence of heteroskedasticity.

Table 4. Glejser Test Results

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3,723	0,642		5,800	0,000
Product Quality (X ₁)	-0,013	0,028	-0,040	0,458	0,648
Brand Image (X ₂)	-0,028	0,036	-0,064	-0,768	0,444
Brand Ambassador (X ₃)	-0,074	0,40	-0,165	-1,852	0,066

(Source: SPSS 25.0 for Windows Output)

The Glejser test results (Table 4) show that the product quality variable (X1) has a significance value of 0.648, the brand image variable (X2) has a significance value of 0.444, and the brand ambassador variable (X3) has a significance value of 0.066. All significance values are greater than 0.05, indicating that the regression model used in this study does not exhibit heteroskedasticity.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis in this study is used to determine the direction and magnitude of the effect of product quality (X1), brand image (X2), and brand ambassador (X3) on MS Glow purchasing decisions (Y) in Baturiti.

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	0,315	1,037		0,762	0,762
Product Quality (X ₁)	0,225	0,045	0,299	5,020	0,000
Brand Image (X ₂)	0,289	0,059	0,284	4,916	0,000

THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT QUALITY, BRAND IMAGE, AND BRAND AMBASSADOR ON MS GLOW PURCHASE DECISIONS IN BATURITI, TABANAN REGENCY, BALI PROVINCE

Ni Ketut Oni Widarianti et al

<i>Brand Ambassador (X₃)</i>	0,369	0,065	0,351	5,700	0,000
---	-------	-------	-------	-------	-------

(Source: SPSS 25.0 for Windows Output)

Based on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis presented in Table 5, the constant (α) is 0.315. The regression coefficients are 0.225 for product quality (β_1), 0.289 for brand image (β_2), and 0.369 for brand ambassador (β_3), with an error coefficient (ϵ) of 1.037. Based on these values, the multiple linear regression equation for this study can be formulated as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \epsilon$$

$$Y = 0,315 + 0,225 X_1 + 0,289 X_2 + 0,369 X_3 + 1,037$$

The interpretation of the multiple linear regression analysis results is as follows:

1. The constant value (α) of 0.315 indicates the purchasing decision value when the product quality (X_1), brand image (X_2), and brand ambassador (X_3) variables are assumed unchanged or equal to zero. This condition illustrates that without the influence of these three independent variables, the purchasing decision value is 0.315.
2. The regression coefficient for product quality (β_1) of 0.225 indicates a positive effect on purchasing decisions. Each one-unit increase in product quality will increase the purchasing decision by 0.225, assuming brand image and brand ambassador variables remain constant.
3. The regression coefficient for brand image (β_2) of 0.289 indicates a positive effect on purchasing decisions. Each one-unit increase in brand image will increase the purchasing decision by 0.289, assuming product quality and brand ambassador variables remain constant.
4. The regression coefficient for the brand ambassador variable (β_3) of 0.369 indicates a positive effect on purchasing decisions. Each one-unit increase in brand ambassador will increase the purchasing decision by 0.369, assuming product quality and brand image remain constant.
5. The error coefficient (ϵ) of 1.037 indicates the influence of other variables outside of product quality, brand image, and brand ambassador that also affect MS Glow purchasing decisions in Baturiti.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is used to measure the extent to which the independent variables contribute to the dependent variable.

Table 6. Results of the Coefficient of Determination (R²) Test

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0,742 ^a	0,550	0,543	2,509

(Source: SPSS 25.0 for Windows Output)

Based on Table 6, the correlation coefficient (R) is 0.742, and the adjusted R² value is 0.550 or 55.0%. This indicates that product quality, brand image, and brand ambassador simultaneously contribute 55.0% to purchasing decisions, while the remaining 45.0% is influenced by variables outside this research model.

Hypothesis Testing

Partial Test (t-test)

The t-test was conducted to determine whether product quality (X_1), brand image (X_2), and brand ambassador (X_3) partially affect MS Glow purchasing decisions (Y) in Baturiti. The decision criteria are:

1. If t-count > t-table or sig < 0.05, it indicates a partial influence of X on Y.
2. If t-count < t-table or sig > 0.05, it indicates no partial influence of X on Y.

THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT QUALITY, BRAND IMAGE, AND BRAND AMBASSADOR ON MS GLOW PURCHASE DECISIONS IN BATURITI, TABANAN REGENCY, BALI PROVINCE

Ni Ketut Oni Widarianti et al

Table 7. Partial Test Results (t-Test)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0,315	1,037		0,762	0,762
	Product Quality (X ₁)	0,225	0,045	0,299	5,020	0,000
	Brand Image (X ₂)	0,289	0,059	0,284	4,916	0,000
	Brand Ambassador (X ₃)	0,369	0,065	0,351	5,700	0,000

(Source: SPSS 25.0 for Windows Output)

Based on Table 7, the results of the t-test lead to the following conclusions:

1. First Hypothesis Test (H₁)

The first hypothesis indicates that the product quality variable (X₁) has a t-count value of 5.020 with a significance level of 0.000. Since t-count (5.020) > t-table (1.973) and the significance value < 0.05, H₀ is rejected. Therefore, it can be concluded that product quality has a positive and significant effect on MS Glow purchasing decisions.

2. Second Hypothesis Test (H₂)

The second hypothesis shows that the brand image variable (X₂) has a t-count value of 4.916 with a significance level of 0.000. Because t-count (4.916) > t-table (1.973) and the significance value < 0.05, H₀ is rejected. This indicates that brand image has a positive and significant effect on MS Glow purchasing decisions.

3. Third Hypothesis Test (H₃)

The third hypothesis demonstrates that the brand ambassador variable (X₃) has a t-count value of 5.700 with a significance level of 0.000. Since t-count (5.700) > t-table (1.973) and the significance value < 0.05, H₀ is rejected. Therefore, the brand ambassador has a positive and significant effect on MS Glow purchasing decisions.

Simultaneous Test (F-test)

The F-test is conducted to assess whether all independent variables in the model collectively influence the dependent variable. The decision criteria for the F-test are as follows:

1. Reject H₀ if F-count > F-table or the significance value < 0.05, indicating that product quality (X₁), brand image (X₂), and brand ambassador (X₃) simultaneously affect MS Glow purchasing decisions (Y).
2. Accept H₀ if F-count < F-table or the significance value > 0.05, indicating no simultaneous effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

Table 8. Simultaneous Test Results (F-Test)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1356,938	3	452,313	71,801	0,000 ^b
	Residual	1108,723	176	6,300		
	Total	2465,661	179			

(Source: SPSS 25.0 for Windows Output)

Based on Table 8, the F-count value is 71.801, which is greater than the F-table value of 2.660, and the significance value is 0.000 < 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that product quality (X₁), brand image (X₂), and brand ambassador (X₃) simultaneously have a significant effect on MS Glow purchasing decisions (Y) in Baturiti.

Discussion

The Effect of Product Quality on MS Glow Purchasing Decisions in Baturiti

The results of this study indicate that product quality (X₁) has a positive and significant effect on MS Glow purchasing decisions (Y) in Baturiti. This is evidenced by a t-count value of 5.020, which is greater than the t-table value of 1.973, with a significance level of 0.000 (<0.05). Therefore, the hypothesis stating that product quality positively and significantly affects purchasing decisions is accepted. In other words, the higher the perceived product quality, the stronger the consumer’s purchasing decision for MS Glow products. Theoretically, according to Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller, product quality refers to a product’s ability to perform its functions,

including durability, reliability, accuracy, ease of use, and other attributes that provide value and satisfaction to consumers. High-quality products enhance consumer satisfaction, build trust, and ultimately influence purchasing decisions and customer loyalty. In this study, product quality was analyzed through six indicators: performance, durability, conformance, features, reliability, and aesthetics. Performance reflects MS Glow's ability to fulfill claims such as brightening and moisturizing the skin. Durability indicates that the product can be used for a certain period without significant quality deterioration, providing economic value to consumers. Conformance refers to the product's ability to meet quality standards and consumer expectations, including safety and consistent results. Feature variety is demonstrated through different products, such as serums, day creams, and night creams, allowing consumers to select according to their skin needs.

Reliability is reflected by minimal side effects and consistent benefits. Product aesthetics, including attractive packaging design, pleasant fragrance, and comfortable texture, contribute to a positive consumer experience. When linked to purchasing decision indicators, the influence of product quality can be explained further. Purchasing decisions were measured using four indicators: decisiveness in choosing a product, habitual purchasing, recommending to others, and repurchasing. First, high product quality increases consumer confidence in choosing a product. Consumers who are confident in the effectiveness and safety of the product are more likely to choose MS Glow over other brands. Second, consistent quality forms habitual purchasing because positive usage experiences encourage consumers to repurchase when needed. Third, satisfied consumers are more willing to recommend the product to others, expanding influence through word-of-mouth communication. Fourth, maintained product quality promotes repurchasing intentions because consumers directly experience benefits and satisfaction.

These findings are consistent with previous studies. Sarifuddin *et al.*, (2025) demonstrated that product quality positively affects purchasing decisions. A. Isnaini *et al.* (2024) and Arsyah *et al.*, (2024) also confirmed that product quality significantly influences purchasing decisions for cosmetic and skincare products. Additionally, Syafrinaldy & Akbarina, (2024) found that product quality affects both loyalty and purchasing decisions for skincare products. This alignment strengthens the empirical evidence that product quality is a key determinant in shaping consumer purchasing decisions (Asthika & Ariasih, 2025). Overall, this study confirms that improving product quality in terms of performance, durability, conformance, feature variety, reliability, and aesthetics enhances decisiveness, fosters habitual purchasing, encourages recommendations, and strengthens repurchasing. Therefore, product quality becomes a strategic factor for MS Glow in increasing consumer purchasing decisions in Baturiti and maintaining competitiveness in the skincare industry.

The Effect of Brand Image on MS Glow Purchasing Decisions in Baturiti

The results of this study indicate that brand image (X_2) has a positive and significant effect on MS Glow purchasing decisions (Y) in Baturiti. This is evidenced by a t-count value of 4.916, which is greater than the t-table value of 1.973, with a significance level of 0.000 (<0.05). Therefore, the hypothesis stating that brand image positively and significantly affects purchasing decisions is accepted. In other words, the stronger the brand image of MS Glow in the eyes of consumers, the higher their purchasing decisions for the product. Brand image plays a crucial role in shaping consumer perceptions, building trust, and influencing purchasing decisions, particularly for skincare products, where brand reputation is highly valued. Brand image was analyzed through four main indicators: brand identity, brand personality, brand association, and brand benefits and competence. Brand identity includes physical elements that help consumers recognize MS Glow, such as logos, packaging colors, slogans, and corporate imagery. Consumers in Baturiti can quickly identify MS Glow due to consistent packaging, clear logos, and prominent branding across various sales media. A strong brand identity facilitates consumer differentiation of MS Glow from other skincare products, enhancing confidence in product selection.

Brand personality reflects MS Glow's distinctive character, creating an emotional connection with consumers. Consumers perceive MS Glow as professional, modern, and caring about users' skin health. A personality aligned with consumer characteristics and lifestyles fosters repeat purchasing habits and strengthens loyalty. Brand associations arise from elements linked to MS Glow, such as consistent product quality, support from brand ambassadors, regular promotions, and participation in social activities. Consumers associate MS Glow with safe, effective, and trendy skincare products. These positive associations increase consumer trust and encourage recommendations to others. Brand benefits and competence encompass the tangible and emotional value perceived by consumers, such as healthier skin, a brighter appearance, and aesthetic satisfaction. These advantages motivate consumers to purchase not only based on function but also on emotional and psychological value, encouraging repurchase and differentiating MS Glow from competitors. When directly related to purchasing decision indicators, the influence of brand image is evident across four aspects. First, decisiveness in choosing a

product increases because consumers have greater confidence in MS Glow's quality and reputation compared to other brands. Second, consistent personality and associations foster habitual repurchasing. Third, positive associations and strong brand reputation encourage consumers to recommend the product to others, both directly and via social media. Fourth, product benefits and advantages strengthen consumers' intention to repurchase in the future. These findings align with previous research. Banurea & Purbawati, (2024) demonstrated that brand image significantly influences skincare product purchasing decisions. Putri & Ramadhan (2024) and Danuarta & Yulianthini, (2025) found that both brand image and brand ambassador positively affect purchasing decisions, highlighting the importance of brand image and representative figures in shaping consumer perceptions. Setiawan & Lestari (2023) also confirmed that brand image has a significant effect on purchasing decisions. Thus, this study reinforces the relevance of brand image indicators in the context of MS Glow in Baturiti. By strengthening brand image through consistent identity, a personality aligned with consumers, positive associations, and tangible product benefits and advantages, MS Glow can enhance decisiveness in choosing, habitual purchasing, recommendations, and repurchases. This strategy is crucial for maintaining MS Glow's position as a leading skincare product and sustaining consumer preference in Baturiti.

The Effect of Brand Ambassador on MS Glow Purchasing Decisions in Baturiti

The results of this study indicate that brand ambassador (X_3) has a positive and significant effect on MS Glow purchasing decisions (Y) in Baturiti. This is evidenced by a t -count value of 5.700, which is greater than the t -table value of 1.973, with a significance level of 0.000 (<0.05). Therefore, the hypothesis stating that brand ambassador positively and significantly affects purchasing decisions is accepted. In other words, the more effective a brand ambassador is in representing and promoting MS Glow, the higher the consumer's purchasing decision for the product. The role of a brand ambassador is critical because they can influence consumer perceptions, build trust, and stimulate both emotional and rational purchase intentions.

The MS Glow brand ambassador was analyzed using four indicators according to Kertamukti, (2015), Dewi & Putra, (2024), Dita & Ariasih, (2025), Fathan et al., (2017): visibility, credibility, attraction, and power. Visibility reflects the extent to which the brand ambassador is recognized by the public. In Baturiti, the celebrity or influencer representing MS Glow has a large and widespread following, making their promotional messages easily noticed, remembered, and followed by consumers. This popularity increases the likelihood of consumers trusting the product and deciding to purchase. Credibility represents the expertise, knowledge, and competence of the brand ambassador in conveying information about MS Glow. Consumers perceive the brand ambassador as knowledgeable regarding the product's benefits and usage, enhancing trust in promotional messages and reinforcing confidence in product quality. Attraction encompasses the brand ambassador's physical appearance, personality, and communication style, which create an emotional appeal to consumers. MS Glow's brand ambassadors are perceived as attractive and communicative, allowing consumers to form an emotional connection and feel motivated to follow product recommendations.

Power reflects the ability of the brand ambassador to influence consumers' attitudes, thoughts, and perceptions toward MS Glow. An effective brand ambassador can create positive brand perceptions, assure consumers of product quality, and encourage purchasing decisions (Mahadewi & Yulianthini, 2024). This influence generates a significant persuasive effect, making consumers more likely to trust and choose MS Glow over competing products. When linked to purchasing decision indicators, the influence of brand ambassadors can be observed in four main aspects. First, consumers' decisiveness in choosing a product increases because credible and popular brand ambassadors reinforce confidence in MS Glow. Second, the visibility and attractiveness of the brand ambassador promote habitual repurchasing. Third, positive associations formed through promotional activities and brand ambassador reputation encourage consumers to recommend the product to others. Fourth, the brand ambassador's ability to influence perceptions and purchase interest strengthens consumers' intention to repurchase in the future.

These findings align with previous studies. Wibowo & Putra, (2024) found that brand ambassadors have a positive effect on purchasing decisions. H. Habibulloh & Gunawan, (2024) demonstrated that brand ambassadors and brand awareness significantly affect purchasing decisions. Syafrinaldy & Akbarina, (2024) confirmed that product quality and brand ambassadors simultaneously influence consumer loyalty and purchasing behavior in skincare products. Thus, these findings reinforce the strategic relevance of brand ambassadors in shaping MS Glow consumer behavior in Baturiti. Strengthening brand ambassadors through visibility, credibility, attraction, and power consistently enhances product selection decisiveness, habitual purchasing, recommendations, and

repurchases. This strategy is essential to expand market reach, maintain MS Glow's position as a leading skincare product, and increase consumer loyalty and purchasing decisions in Baturiti.

The Effect of Product Quality, Brand Image, and Brand Ambassador on MS Glow Purchasing Decisions in Baturiti

The study results indicate that the variables of product quality (X_1), brand image (X_2), and brand ambassador (X_3) simultaneously have a significant effect on MS Glow purchasing decisions (Y) in Baturiti District. The F-count value of 71.801 is greater than the F-table value of 2.660, with a significance level of 0.000 (<0.05). This result confirms that the three independent variables collectively contribute to influencing consumer purchasing decisions. In other words, improvements in product quality, brand image, and the effectiveness of brand ambassadors together drive consumers to choose and purchase MS Glow. Product quality influences purchasing decisions through indicators such as performance, durability, conformance, product features, reliability, and aesthetics (Suastini & Yulianthini, 2025). Consumers in Baturiti perceive MS Glow products as consistently high-quality, safe to use, and in line with their expectations. The variety of product features, durability, and attractive appearance increase consumer satisfaction and confidence in their purchasing decisions.

Brand image contributes through brand identity, brand personality, brand association, and brand benefits and competence. Consumers perceive MS Glow as a professional, modern, and reliable brand. Strong brand identity and personality, along with positive associations with product quality and promotions, build consumer trust and increase brand loyalty. Brand ambassadors strengthen the previous two variables through visibility, credibility, attraction, and power. The effectiveness of brand ambassadors in promoting MS Glow ensures that marketing messages are more easily accepted, trusted, and remembered by consumers. Their popularity, credibility, and attractiveness create emotional connections, while their persuasive power drives real purchasing decisions.

Simultaneously, the combination of high product quality, strong brand image, and effective brand ambassadors explains 55.0% of the variance in MS Glow purchasing decisions (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.550$), while the remaining 45.0% is influenced by other factors outside the study model. These findings are consistent with previous research. Putri & Ramadhan (2024) found that brand ambassadors and brand image significantly affect skincare product purchasing decisions. Syafrinaldy & Akbarina, (2024) and Yasana & Ariasih, (2025) confirmed that product quality and brand ambassadors simultaneously influence consumer loyalty and purchasing behavior. Arsyah *et al.*, (2024) also showed that product quality and brand image together positively affect purchasing decisions. These results indicate that MS Glow's marketing strategy cannot rely on a single factor but must emphasize guaranteed product quality, a strong brand image, and effective use of brand ambassadors. The synergy of these three factors enhances positive consumer perceptions, builds trust, and encourages purchasing decisions. Therefore, MS Glow management must maintain consistent product quality, strengthen brand image through appropriate promotion and communication, and maximize the role of brand ambassadors to sustain and increase sales in the Baturiti market.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the hypothesis testing that has been conducted, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Product quality has a positive and significant effect on the purchasing decisions of MS Glow products in Baturiti. This indicates that the better the product quality perceived by consumers, the higher their tendency to make a purchase.
2. Brand image has a positive and significant effect on the purchasing decisions of MS Glow products in Baturiti, indicating that positive perceptions and a strong brand reputation can increase consumers' purchase intentions.
3. Brand ambassador has a positive and significant effect on the purchasing decisions of MS Glow products in Baturiti, meaning that the presence of a brand ambassador is able to influence consumers' attitudes and purchase intentions.
4. Product quality, brand image, and brand ambassador simultaneously have a significant effect on the purchasing decisions of MS Glow products in Baturiti. Therefore, these three variables constitute important factors in the company's marketing strategy.

REFERENCES

- Amstrong, G., & Kotler, P. (2012). *Dasar-Dasar Pemasaran. Jilid I*. Prenhalindo.
- Andika, I. M. A., & Putra, K. E. S. (2025). Pengaruh persepsi konsumen dan brand ambassador terhadap keputusan pembelian sepatu Converse di kalangan mahasiswa Undiksha. *Prospek: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 7(3), 981–990.
- Anggarawati, P. A., & Putra, K. E. S. (2024). Peran citra merek dalam memediasi pengaruh kualitas produk terhadap keputusan pembelian pada Citra Hand and Body Lotion. *Prospek: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 6(1), 82–90.
- Ariasih, M. P. (2025). Pengaruh kualitas produk dan promosi terhadap keputusan pembelian pelembab wajah Skintific di Queen Beauty Singaraja. *Bisma: Jurnal Manajemen*, 11(2).
- Arsya, A. F., Juliag, A. R., Purwida, E. P. W., & Sakdiyah, S. H. (2024). Perkembangan konsumsi skincare pada wanita. *Journal Beauty and Cosmetology (JBC)*, 5(2), 38–41.
- Arta, I. W. S., Yulianthini, N. N., & Heryanda, K. K. (2017). Pengaruh kualitas produk dan harga serta citra merek terhadap keputusan pembelian. *Jurnal Manajemen Indonesia*, 5(2).
- Asthika, I. K. A. W., & Ariasih, M. P. (2025). Pengaruh citra merek dan kualitas produk terhadap keputusan pembelian mobil Gran Max di Astra Daihatsu Singaraja. *Prospek: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 7(2), 451–461.
- Banurea, P. C., & Purbawati, D. (2024). Pengaruh brand image dan negatif electronic word of mouth terhadap keputusan penggunaan jasa ekspedisi JNE di Kota Semarang. *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, 13(1), 99–108.
- Danuarta, S. N., & Yulianthini, N. N. (2025). Pengaruh citra merek dan kesadaran merek terhadap keputusan pembelian smartphone merek iPhone di Kota Singaraja. *Prospek: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 7(2), 400–410.
- Dewi, M. C. L., & Putra, K. E. S. (2024). Pengaruh brand ambassador dan kualitas produk terhadap keputusan pembelian produk kosmetik (studi pada konsumen Oriflame di Kecamatan Buleleng). *Bisma: Jurnal Manajemen*, 10(1), 1–7.
- Dinnie, K. (2015). *Nation branding: Concepts, issues* (practice). Routledge.
- Dita, N. K. A. N., & Ariasih, M. P. (2025). Pengaruh brand ambassador dan electronic word of mouth terhadap keputusan pembelian pelembab wajah Somethinc di Kota Singaraja. *Bisma: Jurnal Manajemen*, 11(2), 703–713.
- Doe, J. (2023). Apa itu skin minimalism? Memahami tren kecantikan 2023 yang tak boleh dilewatkan. In *Ellaskincare Blog*.
- Fathan, R. A., Yulianthini, N. N., & Suci, N. M. (2017). Pengaruh citra merek dan kualitas produk terhadap keputusan pembelian deodoran pria merek Axe pada mahasiswa Fok, Undiksha. *Jurnal Manajemen Indonesia*, 5(2).
- Firmansyah, A. (2018). *Perilaku konsumen*. Deepublish.
- Gallinaro, V. (2023). Skin minimalism – New trend in 2023. In *Esse & Co Blog*.
- Ghozali, I. (2011). *Aplikasi analisis multivariate dengan program SPSS* (4th ed.). Universitas Diponegoro.
- Habibulloh, B. A., Santoso, A., & Pramana, A. C. (2024). Pengaruh social media marketing dan brand awareness terhadap keputusan pembelian produk keripik pisang “Sang Dewa” pada CV. Dewa Snack. *Jurnal Perilaku Dan Strategi Bisnis*, 8, 29630–29638.
- Habibulloh, H., & Gunawan, W. H. (2024). Analisis pengaruh brand ambassador dan brand awareness terhadap keputusan pembelian sabun pemutih Lux dengan variabel minat beli sebagai variabel intervening. *Jurnal Perilaku Dan Strategi Bisnis*, 12(1), 1–15.
- Hata, M., & Huda, N. (2024). Pengaruh brand image, product quality, dan hedonic lifestyle terhadap purchase decision iPhone di kota. *Jurnal*, 17(2), 2149–2163.
- Isnaini, A., Sudianti, D., Rismawati, J., Shevyani, N., Putri, S. A., & Purnamawati, D. R. (2024). Pengaruh keterlibatan influencer dan social media marketing terhadap keputusan pembelian brand skincare Skintific. *JEBI: Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 2(7), 898–905.
- Karina. (2023). Pengaruh kualitas pelayanan dan kepuasan pelanggan terhadap loyalitas pelanggan. *Business and Entrepreneurship Journal (BEJ)*, 4(2), 36–40.
- Kasinem. (2020). Pengaruh kepercayaan dan kualitas pelayanan terhadap kepuasan konsumen pada Hotel Bukit Serele Lahat. *Jurnal Manajemen*, 1(1), 1–11.
- Kertamukti, R. (2015). Peran brand ambassador dalam strategi pemasaran. *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran*, 10(2), 45–53.

THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT QUALITY, BRAND IMAGE, AND BRAND AMBASSADOR ON MS GLOW PURCHASE DECISIONS IN BATURITI, TABANAN REGENCY, BALI PROVINCE

Ni Ketut Oni Widarianti **et al**

- Kotler, P. (2007). *Manajemen pemasaran* (12th ed.). Indeks–Prentice Hall.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2012). *Manajemen pemasaran* (13th ed.). Erlangga.
- Lea-Greenwood, G. (2012). *Fashion marketing communications*. Wiley Blackwell.
- Mahadewi, M. M. S., & Yulianthini, N. N. (2024). Pengaruh citra merek dan kualitas produk terhadap keputusan pembelian Ms Glow di Singaraja. *Prospek: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 6(3).
- Nugroho, S. (2003). *Perilaku konsumen*. Kencana Prenada Media Group.
- Puspitasari, N., Novanka, A., & Hidayat, S. (2024). Draf Laporan Publikasi Riset Potensi Pasar Analisis Strategi Pasar Pada Produk Scarlett. *Digital Bisnis: Jurnal Publikasi Ilmu Manajemen Dan E-Commerce*, 3(1), 98–115.
- Sarifuddin, T., Akkas, N., & Janudin, I. S. A. (2025). Pengaruh Sosial Media Marketing dan Brand Image Terhadap Pembelian Produk Nasa pada Toko VCN Store Palu The Influence of Social Media Marketing and Brand Image on Purchases of Nasa Products at the VCN Store , Palu. *Jurnal Kolaboratif Sains*, 8(1), 17–26. <https://doi.org/10.56338/jks.v8i1.6800>
- Suastini, L. S., & Yulianthini, N. N. (2025). Pengaruh citra merek dan kualitas produk terhadap keputusan pembelian produk skincare Skintific di Toko Kosmetik Queen Beauty Singaraja. *Prospek: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 7(1), 165–174.
- Syafrinaldy, M. R., & Akbarina, F. (2024). PENGARUH KUALITAS PRODUK DAN INFLUENCER MARKETING TERHADAP KEPUTUSAN PEMBELIAN PRODUK SERUM SOMETHINC (Studi Kasus Pada Mahasiswa D-IV Manajemen Pemasaran Politeknik Negeri Malang Tahun Akademik 2023 / 2024). *Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Manajemen*, 2(12), 174–181.
- Tjiptono, F. (2016). *Service, Quality & Satisfaction* (Fourth Edi). ANDI.
- Viatama, B. I., & Rizal, A. (2023). Pengaruh gaya hidup, Brand Image dan kelompok referensi terhadap keputusan pembelian. *Ekonomis: Journal of Economics and Business*, 7(1), 324–328.
- Wibowo, B. G., & Putra, A. B. (2024). Pengaruh E Wom, brand image dan influencer terhadap keputusan pembelian pada Tokopedia. *MASMAN: Master Manajemen*, 2(2), 167–176.
- Yasana, I. K. N., & Ariasih, M. P. (2025). Pengaruh citra merek dan kualitas produk terhadap keputusan pembelian smartpone iPhone di Kota Singaraja. *Prospek: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 7(2).